

DELAMINATION OF COMPOSITE MATERIALS. FRACTURE MECHANICS

AND DAMAGE EVALUATION

D. LEFEBVRE et C. BATHIAS

UNIVERSITE DE TECHNOLOGIE
B.P. 233 - 60206 COMPIEGNE FRANCE

INTRODUCTION

As composites are being used more and more in the aerospace industry, their mechanical and fracture behavior must be clearly understood.

In this study, a variety of fatigue loading cases were examined in graphite epoxy composites and glass-epoxy composites. The mechanics of delamination and the resulting damage patterns were investigated.

Our goal was not to contribute to a fractographic atlas. Instead we attempted to understand the locus of failure and the relationship of the damage pattern to the microstructure.

Fractography as well as various non-destructive testing methods were used and the resulting findings were analysed, leading to a qualitative delamination model.

MECHANICS OF DELAMINATION

1. Experimental

1.1. Materials. Materials investigated in this study were graphite-epoxy laminates and glass-epoxy fabric composites.

The laminated graphite-epoxy laminates were made of unidirectional plies, reinforced with T300 carbon fibers and embedded in a 5208 or 914 epoxy matrix. The stacking sequence was $(0^\circ, +45^\circ, -45^\circ, 90^\circ, 90^\circ, -45^\circ, +45^\circ, 0^\circ)_{17}$, resulting in quasi-isotropic characteristics at the specimen scale.

Our fabric composite was made of 56 "Satin 5" woven plies with a quasi-isotropic $(0/45)_{ns}$ layup. Its warp and fill strands were reinforced with glass fibers and 5208 or 914 epoxy resins were used.

1.2. Test specimens and mechanical testing. Macromechanics tests were run to measure the delamination fracture toughness. Thus, both materials were fatigue tested at frequencies averaging 5 Hz in the form of DCB specimens fitted with a built-in teflon starter so as to initiate a planar inter-

laminar crack along the neutral axis of the beam and perpendicular to the loading axis. The DCB specimens were cut out from Aerospatiale-manufactured panels.

Dimensions of the beams were 20X20X90 mm for mode I specimens and 20X 20X200 mm for mode II specimens. Interlaminar crack length was monitored visually on the free edges of the beam with the help of a white contrast-enhancing coating.

Uniaxial tension was applied by means of appropriate grip linkages controlled by a servohydraulic system. Load range was 2 tons. The load displacement history was interrupted frequently to obtain unload / reload compliances.

All tests were conducted in load control until catastrophic failure occurred.

2. Fracture mechanics of delamination

2.1. Method. Our approach is based on concepts of Linear-Elastic Fracture Mechanics carried out from isotropic materials. Indeed, various geometric and material properties lead us to assume that these concepts could be applied successfully :

Firstly, the interlaminar crack is essentially planar and the crack tip is evenly distributed across the width of our specimens. Secondly, the crack plane is normal to the loading axis. Thirdly, the beam behaves elastically at the macroscopic scale.

Therefore, the stress intensity factor (ΔK) and energy release rate (ΔG) were computed from variables such as, applied loads, specimen geometry and crack size, using classical polynomial forms :

$$\text{Mode I} \quad K_I = \frac{4 P}{Bh^{3/2}} (3 a^2 + 3.84 ha + 1.22 h^2)^{1/2} \quad (1)$$

$$G_I = \frac{Ka^2}{E} + \frac{P}{B\mu s'} \quad (2)$$

$$\text{Mode II} \quad K_{II} = \frac{3 Pa}{2 Bh^{3/2}} \quad (3)$$

$$G_{II} = \frac{Ka^2}{E} \quad (4)$$

B = beam width

h = beam half- thickness

a = interlaminar crack length

E, μ = elastic moduli

S' = 5/6 cross section area of the beam

Energy release rates obtained with compliance tests were found to be in accordance with the ΔK values.

2.2. Results and discussion. The stress intensity factor was correlated with the delamination rate (da/dn), which was measured visually. This approach enabled us to control the mechanical parameters in our tests and thus allowed us to compare toughness characteristics of different materials. Variables studied were ply texture (unidirectional or woven), resin ductility (5208 or 914), state of stress (mode I or mode II) loading ratio ($R = F_{min}/ F_{max}$).

Finding

Despite the inevitable scattering due to the structure of the material and the crack measurement method, it was found that a Paris-Like propagation law - ie : $da/dn \propto \Delta K^m$ - was obeyed by the main interlaminar crack.

In both mode I and mode II tests, this power law was obeyed for delamination rates ranging from 10^{-5} to 10^{-2} mm/cycle. Numerous plots corresponding to different variables were obtained. (Figures 1 to 5).

Fig. 1. T 300/914 quasi-isotropic layup ; X sp. n°23, 0 sp. n°19, + sp. n°17; Mode I : R = 0,1 f = 10 Hz.

Fig. 2. Mode II test ; Loading ratio = 0.1; iso 914 specimens. N° 2 and N° 6; $da/dn = \lambda \Delta K^m$ m=3; correction factor = 0.66; Teflon starter between 0° and 45° plies.

Fig. 3. Carbon epoxy composite : quasi isotropic layup made of unidirectional plies; Summary of mode I and mode II delamination tests.

Fig. 5. Apparent stiffness vs. delamination length

It is worthwhile to take note that for a given material, mode I (peel) is more damaging than mode II (figure 4).

Fig. 4. Glass epoxy composite : quasi isotropic layup made of woven plies
Summary of mode I and mode II delamination tests

Furthermore, for a given set of mechanical parameters, our woven fabric composites exhibited a higher toughness than laminated carbon-epoxy composites.

As the loading ratio (P_{min}/P_{max}) increased, the slope of da/dn vs. ΔK increased. Thus, for a given ΔK , the delamination rate decreases with lower loadings.

Finally, for a given stress state, the delamination rate was slightly higher in the 5208 resin than in the modified 914 epoxy resin, evidently due to the lower resin toughness.

1. Mode I fracture surfaces and mode I free-edge cracking (Carbon-epoxy laminates)

Whatever the location of the interlaminar teflon starter, it was found that delamination would always favor the nearest 0°/45° interfacial region and stabilize in it after 20 mm of initiation mode, or so.

The fracture surface would show :

Firstly, interlaminar resin-rich regions marked with fiber imprints left over by the debonded ply, interspersed between regions where fibers from the underlying ply or the upper ply, surface into the interlaminar space.

Secondly, regions exhibiting meshes peeled out of the upper ply.

Most features described above resulted from crack branching mechanisms in which delamination periodically interacted with sublaminar transverse cracking.

Figure 6 and 7 schematically show the fracture surface and the observed free edge cracking sequences.

Fig. 6. carbon-epoxy laminate (fatigued in mode I)
Fracture surface and free edge
Cracking

Fig. 7. Carbon epoxy laminate (fatigued in mode I) Sp N° 29; Free edge cracking sequence showing delamination combined with through the thickness cracking in the 45° oriented laminate.

In figure 7, the crack was initiated at a + 45°/ - 45° interface (mode I, R = 0.1.)

Interestingly enough, skewed free edge cracks propagated in the 2 opposite directions, even in areas remote from the delamination front. Besides, emerging cracks on the free edges remained discontinuous until the final stages of fracture. These discontinuities developed into residual bundles bridging the crack faces behind the crack tip. It is thought that these bridges do not affect toughness significantly. As the crack opening increased, bundles spanning the two faces were eventually bent until they broke. Thus fiber breakage visible on fracture surfaces is not a leading failure mechanism but rather a secondary event occurring at the final stages of cleavage, when many transverse cracks have coalesced into bridging bundles.

Since the delamination rate (da/dn) was computed by averaging crack lengths as measured on the free edges, one easily understands why scattering was inevitable in our macroscopic mechanical analysis. Indeed, the delamination rate of emerging cracks would fluctuate a great deal locally, typically decreasing when skewed cracks would propagate in the bridged area behind the main front.

Our study did not include transient delamination during the initiation phase, when the damage state is not clearly established. The end of this transient mode would always be marked by a sudden fall in the apparent stiffness of the beam (figure 5).

2. X-ray radiography of damaged carbon-epoxy laminates

X-ray radiographs of damaged carbon-epoxy specimens obtained with an enhancement agent, revealed axial cracks and transverse cracks, both ahead of the delamination front (dashed line in figure 8) and extending through plies bordering the existing interlaminar cracks.

Unflawed regions appeared in light grey, sublaminar axial and transverse cracks appeared in black, delaminated interfaces constrained by compressive residual stress were filled with opaque additive and thus appeared in dark grey; finally, delaminated regions filled with air appeared in

white (figure 8).

Fig. 8. Carbon epoxy laminate
Radiograph of damaged specimen N° 31
(with opaque additive)
Fatigue delamination was stopped at
N = 98, 500 cycles.

The dark grey region believed to be constrained by residual stress was about 10 mm wide and was larger close to the free edges of the specimens, just as in metals.

Axial and transverse cracks ahead of the delamination front are believed to be caused by the triaxial stress state prevalent in this region.

Similar features were found on radiographs of fabric composites: cracks ahead of the delamination front were 45° oriented and located between strands of the woven plies.

In both materials, the delamination front was convex, hinting that free edge effects are not negligible in thick composite specimens such as ours.

3. Damage mechanisms in Carbon epoxy laminates, Qualitative micromechanics model

Starting from free edge delamination observations, SEM fractography and X-radiography, we attempted to ascertain the locus of failure and to relate the fracture mode to the microstructure of the material.

No formal distinction was made between transverse cracking (ie : along fiber directions and through the thickness of a ply) and interlaminar cracking between two adjacent plies.

However microcracking, which forms substructures in each ply was clearly distinguished from the two preceding types. Close fractographic examination with a SEM indicated that these microcracks tend to cluster in areas adjacent to main transverse cracks or interlaminar cracks. (Cracks were named "primary", "secondary", or "ternary" according to their orientation.

Primary : Interlaminar crack (horizontal, either interfacial or transverse).

Secondary : Transverse, through the thickness of a 0° ply)

(*

Ternary : Transverse, through the thickness of a 45° ply)

* Note : Transverse = through the thickness + along the fiber direction.

Whenever a crack would be playing a leading role in the damage state it was called "main crack".

On the other hand, microcracks induced by main cracks but playing virtually no role in the failure sequence were called "subcracks". Of course, a subcrack may be primary, secondary or ternary, depending on its orientation.

Main cracks generate subcracks by transferring load to the surrounding matrix material or interlaminar area. (figure 9 and 10)

Consequently : $\left[\begin{array}{l} \text{a main secondary crack may generate ternary subcracks} \\ \text{primary} \text{ --- } \text{ternary} \\ \text{primary} \text{ --- } \text{secondary} \\ \text{ternary} \text{ --- } \text{secondary} \end{array} \right.$

Main crack interactions

See figure 9

Fig. 9. Carbon epoxy laminate ; Mode I delamination pattern on the side capped by 0° meshes

In mode I, main ternary cracks were found to interfere with main primary cracks by causing them to deviate periodically into the adjacent 45° ply. Therefore, due to this interference with main ternary cracks, main primary cracks appear as 45° oriented stripes on the radiographs. (eg.figure 8)

Besides, they emerged on the free edges. Thus, previous free edge delamination findings can be fully explained.

In specimens fatigued in mode II, the crack pattern was found to be essentially the same as in mode I. (See figure 10). Main crack spacing was about the same. However, interference between cracks was minor, leading to much smoother fracture surfaces.

(1) main secondary crack ; (2) main ternary crack ; (3) ternary subcracks ; (4) (5) main primary (either interfacial or transverse) ; (6) secondary subcracks ; (A B C D) = cleavage plane.

Fig. 10. Carbon epoxy laminate ; Mode II Delamination pattern

Radiographs of mode II specimens also show :

1. long 0° transverse cracks (secondary) extending beyond the delamination front.
2. 45° transverse cracks.
3. horizontal cracks (primary) either through 0° plies or at the + 45°/-45° interface.

The only noticeable difference is the presence of ternary subcracks emerging on the delamination interface.

Both in mode I and in mode II, main primary cracks (eventually merging into full cleavage) were confined within the 0°/45° interfacial region, whatever the location of the teflon starter.

4. DAMAGE MECHANISMS IN GLASS EPOXY FABRIC COMPOSITES

Radiography was performed on a fabric specimen fatigued in mode I. Then, various 0° and 45° cross sections obtained with standard metallographic techniques, were investigated with a SEM. (See figure 11,12).

Fig. 11. Specimen N° 45 - glass-epoxy fabric Mode I; Mode I - $R = 0, 1$

Fig. 12. Glass epoxy fabric mode II ; Specimen N° 18

Our findings confirmed that delamination runs faster inside the material and forms a convex front. It also favors strand interfaces between $(0^\circ, 90^\circ)$ and $(+ 45^\circ, - 45^\circ)$ woven plies. Furthermore, cracking ahead of the delamination front was viewed in the form of cracks normal to the plies and creeping through 45° strands.

In a second stage, delamination between strands - ie parallel to the woven plies - is thought to occur simultaneously with coalescing between the

initial cracks.

In fabric specimens subjected to mode II fatigue delamination, the damage state as well as the delamination front were found to be the same as in mode I.

Figure 11. Shows initial delamination around 0° strands.

In mode II, the delamination pattern is more complex due, to cracks' natural tendency to deviate towards the maximum shear plane of the beam.

Finally, mode I static fracture resulted in a very uniform delamination front at the interface between the 0° and 45° oriented plies and a lower damage density than that caused by mode I cyclic loading.

Evidently, the tortuous path imposed by the weave may account for the higher toughness of fabric composite mentioned earlier.

5. Plastic deformation in the matrix material

High magnification SEM fractography of delaminated surfaces revealed many interesting plastic deformation features.

Areas propitious to extensive plastic deformation are resin-rich regions, typically between the plies of a laminated carbon epoxy composite or near the warp and fill cross-over of fabric glass-epoxy composites.

When the plastic layer is uniformly distributed as in interlaminar regions, plastic features resemble those observed in fatigue fractured bulk resin specimens.

In figure 13 and 14, fine river markings resulting from the shear yielding of the polymer are shown in residual resin layers sticking on the 45° oriented laminate.

river markings in resin rich region

Fig. 13. Carbon Epoxy Laminate ; Plastic deformations features.

Fig. 14. Carbon Epoxy Laminate ; Plastic deformation features

In fabric composites, fatigue lines are sometimes visible on large resin remnants.

Such evidence is thought to be potentially useful in pointing to cyclic loading as a cause for delamination in composite parts failed in use.

Generally, plastic deformations were found in the form of "river" or "sheaf" markings made of thin nail-like resin strips.

These deformations are more prominent in areas where cracks had to cross a resin-rich region in order to say, connect a through the thickness transverse crack to an interfacial crack. (See figure 13). Elsewhere, in relatively undisturbed interfacial regions on the delamination surface, markings protrude much less.

In all cases, the orientation of these features clearly indicate the macroscopic delamination path :

River-like markings are thought to be formed by slow cracking, whereas sheaf-like markings are thought to be caused by fast cracking. Again, this analogy with bulk resin fracture mechanisms, we believe, would be helpful in finding the delamination direction after accidental failures.

6. Additional evidence to find the delamination direction in mode I fatigued carbon-epoxy composites.

In addition to plastic deformation markings observed at high magnification with a SEM, larger resin features visible optically at low magnification under an adequate lighting, were isolated as further evidence of the macroscopic delamination direction.

Low incidence light oriented axially (0°) gave us shots like the one displayed in figure 15.

Fig. 15. Fracture surface of a carbon epoxy laminate ; subjected to mode I delamination

It was found that the bright resin features correspond to thick resin remnants bordering the protruding 45° oriented bundles nearby. The limit on the (a) side is neat, whereas the limit on side (b) is shredded. Side (a) was formed by an intralaminar crack emerging from the underlying 45° laminate whereas side (b) marks a transition region back to the fiber interface region between the resin layer and the 45° ply. The shredding is probably due to 0° imprints left by the debonded 0° fibers formerly situated above the fracture surface. Thus delamination direction is (a) towards (b).

CONCLUSION

Fracture mechanics of delamination :

The peculiar geometric properties of our cracked specimens along with the macroscopic mechanical properties of the materials used in this study enabled us to assume that linear fracture mechanics could be applied successfully.

Therefore the stress intensity factor (ΔK) was computed from the applied loads and the crack size using classical polynomial forms. This method was confirmed by carrying out compliance tests.

The stress intensity factor was correlated with the delamination rate (da/dn), which was measured experimentally, and numerous plots corresponding to different types of materials and fracture modes were obtained.

Despite the inevitable scattering due to the structure of the material, it was found that (1) a Paris-like propagation law ($da/dn \propto \Delta K^m$) is obeyed by the main interlaminar crack, (2) mode I is more damaging than mode II, (3) woven fabric composites exhibit a higher toughness than laminated carbon epoxy composites, (4) the slope of da/dn vs. ΔK increases with higher loading ratios and the delamination rate is slightly higher with the 5208 resin than with the modified 914 epoxy resin.

Fractography, NDT and fracture behavior :

Detailed post-failure examination using optical microscopy and scanning electron microscopy yielded some information on the propagation mode of macroscopic interlaminar cracks. However, non-destructive investigation methods such as X-ray radiography and X-ray scanning were even more helpful in determining the relationship of the fracture mode to the microstructure

of the material. Indeed, the capability of detect in-depth sublaminar crack patterns as well as to inspect the damaged plies near the crack tip prior to failure, proved invaluable to study the damage mechanisms associated with delamination.

In spite of its depth resolution limitation, X-ray scanning is a very promising tool for obtaining a three dimensional image of damaged zones. This method consists of measuring the density distribution across a selected section of the specimen and thus, gives us a quantitative characterization of the local damage state.

In both graphite-epoxy laminates and glass-epoxy fabric composites, the damage state associated with macroscopic interlaminar cleavage under cyclic loading, consisted of regular arrays of cracks in the epoxy matrix at the sublaminar and microscopic scale. Using data gathered from fractography and non-destructive investigations, an attempt was made to understand the interactions between the various types of cracks. This approach led us to propose a tentative damage and crack propagation model describing the fracture sequence.

At high magnification, fracture surfaces of composite laminates and fabrics exhibited plastic deformation in resin rich areas that could be correlated with the direction of propagation of the interlaminar crack. Other resin features detected at low magnification are thought to be potentially helpful in determining the direction of delamination.

Fiber breakage, although visible at places on the fracture surfaces of both materials was found to play virtually no role in interlaminar failure mechanisms.

REFERENCES

1. Private communication, T.K. O' Brien, "Stiffness change as a nondestructive damage measurement," in Mechanisms of Nondestructive Testing.
2. K.L. Reifsnider, W.W. Stinchcomb and E.G. Henneke, "Defect property relationship in composite laminates," A.F.M.L., Technical Report 76-81, part IV, April 1979.
3. K.L. Reifsnider, and R. Jamison, "Fracture of fatigue-loaded composite laminates," International Journal of Fatigue, October 1982.
4. K.L. Reifsnider, W.W. Stinchcomb and T.K. O'Brien, "Frequency effects on a stiffness based fatigue criterion in flawed composites specimens," Fatigue of Filamentary Composite materials, A.S.T.M. STP 636, American Society for testing and Materials 1977, pp 171-184.
5. S.V. Ramani and D.P. Williams, "Notched and unnotched fatigue behavior of angle-ply graphite/epoxy composites," Fatigue of Filamentary Composite materials, A.S.T.M. STP 636, American Society for testing and Materials 1977, pp 27-46.
6. J.F. Mandell, J.F. Mc Garry, J.Jm and U. Meier 1974, "Fiber orientation, crack velocity, and cyclic loading effects on the mode of crack extension in fiber reinforced plastics," Polymer engineering and science, September 1976, vol. 16, N°9.
7. Private communication, F.X. DE CHARENTENAY, G. Behar, P.Sauve et K. Kami-mura (U.T.C.), P.V. N°40 704, "Mécanismes d'endommagement mécanique dans les matériaux composites carbone-époxy comportant une entaille,".
8. J.D. Whitcomb, "Experimental and analytical study of fatigue damage in Notched Graphite/Epoxy Laminates," Fatigue of fibrous composite materials A.S.T.M. STP 723, American Society for Testing of Materials 1981, pp 48-63.
9. R.B. Pipes, N.J. Pagano, Interlaminar stresses in composite laminates under uniform axial extension, J. and Composite Mat, 1970, 4-pp 538 - 548.
10. M.L. Benzeggagh, Application de la mécanique de la rupture aux matériaux composites, Exemple de la rupture par délamination d'un stratifié, Thèse soutenue le 19 Juin 1980, U.T.C.
11. R.W. Hertzberg, M.D. Skido, J.A. Manson, "Fatigue fracture micromechanisms in Engineering plastics," Ed. A.S.T.M. STP 675 1979, PP 471 - 500.
12. R. Esnault, D. Aliaga, C. Bathias, "Tensile and fatigue damaging and fracture of 2 notched fiber glass and carbone composite materials, J.N.C. 3, Paris 1982.
13. A. Laksimi, C. Bathias, R. Esnault, D. Aliaga, "Etude du seuil de délaminage dans un matériau composite renforcé par fibres de verre," J.N.C. 3, Paris 1982.

